

LEADERSHIP, GOVERNMENT EMPLOYEES EMPOWERMENT, SOCIAL SUPPORT AND GOVERNMENT EMPLOYEES PERFORMANCE AT HOSPITAL BLU TANDUALE BOMBANA REGENCY SOUTH EAST SULAWESI INDONESIA

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Abstract

The aims of the research is to examine the influence of leadership on the performance of government employees through empowerment of government employees and social support on the performance of government employees. The total popuation is 88 people, determination of the sample using the census technique. Methods of data collection using a statement list, with a Likert scale. The result of this research are 1) the leadership had positip and significant effect on government employees empowerment, 2) the leadership had positip significant on social suport, 3) The leadership had positip significant on government employees performance, 4) the government employees empowerment had positip significant on government employees performance, 5) the social suport had positip but not significant on the government employees performet, 6) social suport can't plays a role mediating the effect of leadership on government employees performance, 7) the government employees empowerment plays role in mediating the effect of leadership on government employees performance.

Keywords: Leadership, Government Employees, Empowerment, Social Support and Performance.

INTRODUCTION

Public health services as one of the main tasks of hospitals have an important role in improving public health. Hospitals must be able to provide good services, on the one hand, hospitals must also be able to synergize all health resources they have, including human resources, which include medical personnel, pharmaceutical personnel, nursing and midwifery personnel, public health personnel, environmental health personnel, nutrition personnel, physical therapy personnel, medical technical personnel, and other health personnel (Mujiati and Yuniar, 2016). It requires the support of all individual abilities which are essentially composed of two sets of ability factors, namely physical ability and intellectual ability (Robbins (2015). Employee performance or work achievement is a measure to identify the final results of employee achievement of the tasks carried out in the organization (Robbins and Judge 2018., Santis et al. 2018, Dessler 2017).

Government Employees at BLU Tanduale Hospital, Bombana Regency have an important role in creating stability in an area that is safe, orderly, peaceful and harmonious in social life, as well as the realization of democratic, healthy and polite social life in society. (Profile of BLU Tanduale Hospital, Bombana Regency. 2022). Ironically, based on the facts that occurred from the results of the pre-survey, the empirical gap in this study is that the leadership decisions at the BLU Tanduale Hospital, Bombana Regency, with insufficient human resources, are still top-down, where employees are only implementing policies and should be the spearhead in service, resulting in on Government Employees performance that is not optimal.

Increasing Government Employees performance, Government Employees empowerment, and social support for the organization cannot be separated from the behavior of leaders. Theoretical studies referring to leadership behavior are the result of the synthesis of pathgoal leadership theory (House and Mitchell, 1974), quoted from Robbins and Judge (2017), stating that the task of leaders is to help their followers achieve goals and provide direction as needed. Path-goal theory explains the impact of leader behavior on satisfaction and performance (Luthans, 2011). Consistent with the opinion of Colquitt et al. (2015) that leadership is inspiring followers to commit to a shared vision that gives meaning to work, while developing the potential for achieving personnel performance. Support from previous research findings that have tested the influence of leadership on employee performance by Zeb Ali et al. (2019), Gökhan & Kuzey (2019); Al Suwaidi & Rahman (2019). Elliya (2019), Altunoğlu et al. (2018), Chan (2020) Ouakouak, et al. (2020), Omar Hendro et al (2020), Pujiono et al. (2020), Irma & Hardi (2020), Indra & Ekhsan (2021), Lita Norfiana et al, (2021), Yulyanti Fahrana (2022), found that there is a significant positive influence between leadership on employee performance. However, there are gaps or contradictory research results from Bani Mirza and Hendra (2021) and Ben Sedrine et al. (2020) found that leadership had no significant effect on employee performance. Based on the gaps and contradictions in the research findings, these are caused by variations in the measurement of leadership constructs and employee performance, the objects studied, analysis methods, sample size and the theoretical basis used. Thus, it is an opportunity for researchers to re-examine the influence of leadership variables on employee performance.

This study aims to test and explain the construct of employees empowerment based on employee empowerment theory by adopting a structural or psychological approach that high perceived employee empowerment is positively correlated with employee performance (Bowen and Lawler, 1995; and Chamberlin et al., 2018). (Spreitzer, 1995 and Khan (1997) which are grouped into two different dimensions with seven sub-dimensions, namely structural empowerment (structural framework, managing decisions at work and transparency in sharing information) and psychological empowerment (meaning, competence, self-determination itself and impact).

Social support is also important in efforts to improve employee performance. According to Benjamin (1983), social support is verbal or non-verbal information, advice, real assistance or behavior provided by people who are familiar with the subject in their social environment or in the form of presence and things. Things that can provide emotional benefits or influence the behavior of the recipient. This support can take the form of mutual help, mutual cooperation, reminding each other and caring for each other. Several previous studies found that social support had an effect on performance, Setiawan & Kusmiyanti, (2022).

To further examine the influence of leadership on employee empowerment, social support and employee performance, as well as the mediating role of employee empowerment and social support, a study was conducted taking the research object at BLU Tanduale Hospital, Bombana Regency, Southeast Sulawesi. To be able to determine the quality of human resource performance of employees at RSU BLU Bombana Regency, a study is needed on the Influence of Leadership on the Performance of Civil Servants at BLU Hospital Bombana Regency which is mediated by Employee Empowerment and Social Support.

THEORETICAL REVIEW

Leadership

Leadership is the use of influence without coercion (noncoercive) to shape the goals of a group or organization, motivate behavior towards achieving these goals, and help define the culture of the group or organization (Griffin, 2004). Leadership as the ability to handle other people to obtain maximum results with as little friction as possible and great cooperation, leadership is a creative and directed spirit/moral force (De Hoogh, 2008). Leadership in groups is a very strategic thing to pay attention to in community empowerment efforts through a group approach (Lepak, 2007). Basically, leadership in a group is a person's ability to influence group members to behave as desired by the leader in achieving group goals together.

The Role of Leadership in Organizations

Mintzberg (1975) in his article entitled "The Manager's Job: Folklore and Fact", suggests various types of leadership roles based on authority and formal status obtained from the organization. The leadership roles proposed by Mintzberg (1975) include interpersonal roles, informational roles and decision-making roles. Interpersonal Role (Interpersonal) The role of personal relations where the leader has the role of representing the organization in activities outside the organization. The role of personal relationships is also related to the leader's task of coordinating, controlling, motivating and supporting his subordinates. Apart from that, the leader is a liaison, namely the leader connects personnel at all levels of management. Informational Role (Informational) The role as a leader related to information is the role of the leader as the nerve center of the organization, namely to receive the most up-to-date information and as a disseminator of information to all personnel in the organization. Another information role is that of the manager as a spokesperson to answer questions about the information he has. The Role of the Decision Maker (Decisional) The role of decision maker carried out by the leader is as an entrepreneur, as a person who handles disturbances, as a person who allocates organizational resources, and as a negotiator if conflict occurs within the organization.

Leadership Functions

Apart from having a role, leadership also has a function, according to Nawawi (2006), operationally leadership can be distinguished into five functions, namely instructive function, consultative function, participative function, delegative function and controlling function. There are seven indicators of leadership, namely:

- (1) Self-confidence. Self-confidence is the initial capital for leading others.
- (2) Intelligence. Ability above average, able to analyze problems and opportunities.
- (3) Knowledge of the business (business knowledge). Familiar with the business environment. Having instincts helps in making decisions,
- (4) Emotional Intelligence (emotional intelligence). Can feel, assimilate, understand and regulate one's own emotions,
- (5) Integrity. Trustworthy and able to translate words into actions,
- (6) Drive. Motivation from within to pursue dreams, requires achievement and challenges to always learn,

- (7) Leadership Motivation. Has a high need to share strength or motivation with the team to achieve goals.

Employee Empowerment Concept

Empowerment is a general concept ranging from providing decision-making power and autonomy to employees, to providing strategic resources to employees (Caniëls et al., 2017). Furthermore, Chasanah (2008) states that empowerment is truly meaningful employee involvement. The concept of empowerment comes from two different traditions with the same individual views, namely:

- (1) Freire's pedagogy (1972), which aims to improve the situation of oppressed humans and humanistic psychology by Rogers (1977).

Therefore, the concept of empowerment began to be explained by Rappaport (1981), especially in public health, social work, and represents a bottom-up approach that includes goals and processes. Thus, empowerment is the authority to make decisions in a certain area of operational activities without having to obtain approval from other people. Empowerment is the giving of responsibility and authority from superiors to employees, which involves sharing information and knowledge to guide employees in acting in accordance with organizational goals (Baron and Rue, 2007:24).

Kadarisman (2013) has the same opinion that employee empowerment is an effort by superiors to give trust to their subordinates, as well as encouraging their subordinates to innovate so that they can complete their tasks to the maximum extent possible. Therefore, employee empowerment is an effort to create a safe and comfortable work environment so that employees can make optimal contributions to the organization. Empowerment is an effort that can significantly strengthen confidence in the authority to make decisions in the area of operational activities without having to obtain recognition from other people (Luthan, 2021; Newstorm, 2015; Bowen and Lawler, 1995:74).

To realize the benefits of (structural) empowerment,

- (1) Power to make decisions,
- (2) Information,
- (3) Knowledge, and
- (4) Respect are needed.

In order to achieve the multiplier effect of additives on employee performance. Empowerment is a process to make employees more empowered or more capable of solving problems in their own work so as to produce optimal performance, increase productivity and achieve performance according to Ru et al. (2016) empowerment is a form of decentralization that involves giving subordinates greater authority to make decisions. (Meyerson and Dewettinck, 2012).

Meanwhile, Sedarmayanti (2016) stated that empowerment can encourage initiative and response, so that all problems faced can be adjusted quickly and flexibly. That employee empowerment (individual empowerment) is providing opportunities and encouragement to employees to utilize their talents, skills, resources and experiences to complete work on time.

Social Support

Social support is the resources provided by other people towards individuals which can influence the psychological well-being of the individual concerned (Cohen & Syme in Apollo & Cahyadi, 2012). Meanwhile, according to Baron & Byrne, in Indriani & Sugiasih 2016; Social support is a form of comfort, both physical and psychological, provided by family members or close friends. Social support can be seen from how much social interaction is carried out in carrying out a relationship related to the surrounding environment.

Source of Social Support

According to Azizah (2011), psychosocial treatment for the elderly focuses on social networks and social support. Where this comes from the family. The family is the main social group with which the client has the greatest and closest emotional ties. Social support can be done in the form of a) communicating with each other, b) looking for something to do, and c) if you are on holiday. There are times when someone is closer and more open to their closest friends, thus making it possible for each other to: a) share experiences, b) have a place to express their feelings to each other, and c) build emotional bonds. With the social support variable, it is important for professionals such as nurses, doctors, social workers, clergy. This professional bond will directly generate interest in providing support to clients who are experiencing problems. For example: providing information about treatment, preventing elderly diseases, exercise, approaching God.

Benefits of Social Support

Social support has three types of benefits according to Taylor (in King, 2012), namely:

1. Real help. Families can provide goods and services in stressful situations so that individuals can overcome stress with real help from the people around them.
2. Information Individuals providing support can also recommend specific actions and plans to help someone cope successfully. Information assistance can take the form of information related to the problem being faced.
3. Emotional support in stressful situations individuals often suffer emotionally, which can lead to depression, anxiety, and loss of self-esteem.

The people around him provide support so that the person concerned feels loved, so that he can overcome his problems with greater confidence.

There are six components of social support (Azizah, 2011), namely

- 1) Social cohesion which can create emotional closeness and create a sense of security,
- 2) Social integration which allows people to gain a feeling of belonging to a group and makes it possible to share interests, attention, care for each other,
- 3) Recognition of abilities and expertise and receiving awards,
- 4) Dependence that can be relied on for help,
- 5) Guidance, social support allows people to get information, suggestions or advice,
- 6) Nurturing each other, which makes it possible to obtain prosperity.

The form of social support provided to organizational members (employees) can be in the form of emotional support, appreciation support, instrumental support, and information support (Safarino)

Form of Social Support

Social support is based on the theory of Sarafino (in Kumalasari & Ahyani, 2012) which states that social support consists of four dimensions, namely:

1. Emotional support this support involves expressing empathy and concern for the individual, so that the individual feels comfortable, loved and cared for. This support includes behavior such as providing attention and affection and being willing to listen to other people's complaints.
2. Appreciative support this support involves expressions in the form of statements of agreement and positive assessments of other people's ideas, feelings and performance.
3. Instrumental support: This form of support involves direct assistance, for example in the form of financial assistance or assistance in carrying out certain tasks.
4. Informational support: This informational support can be in the form of suggestions.

Factors that Influence Social Support

According to Myers (in Maslihah, 2011) suggests that there is the three main factors for someone to provide social support are as follows:

1. Empathy participating in other people's distress with the aim of anticipating emotions and behavioral motivations to reduce distress and improve other people's welfare.
2. Social exchange Reciprocal relationship of social behavior between love, service, information. Balance in exchange will produce satisfactory interpersonal relationship conditions. This experience of reciprocal exchange makes individuals more confident that others will provide.
3. Social norms and values during the period of personal growth and development, individuals accept social norms and values from the environment as part of the person's social experience.

These norms and values will direct individuals to behave and explain their obligations in life. In the social environment, individuals are urged to provide help to others in order to develop their social life. In this research, the social support indicators used referring to Sarafino, 1998 include: b. Emotional support: expression of empathy, concern for the individual concerned. c. Appreciation support: forward encouragement of an individual's ideas, expression of appreciation. d. Instrumental support: providing direct material assistance, providing assistance with transportation and school supplies. e. Informative support: providing advice and suggestions, providing instructions.

Employee Performance

Performance is the number and quality of products from the activities of individuals or groups within the company in carrying out their main roles based on the norms and procedures that have been regulated within the company (Torang, 2013). In the health sector, assessing staff performance plays a role in implementing clinical governance, which will ultimately minimize health care costs and ensure the quality of patient care

(Clarke et al, 2013). States that performance is the result of work carried out by employees in accordance with the objectives to be achieved in the work carried out. Meanwhile, Nawawi (2003). Hadari, 2003 states that performance is the work results achieved by a person in carrying out the tasks assigned to him based on skill, experience, seriousness and time. Performance is the result of work functions or activities of a person or group in an organization which is influenced by various factors to achieve organizational goals within a certain time period (Tika, 2006).

Measuring employee performance can be carried out formally or in a structured and automatic system in order to measure, evaluate and understand working conditions, work behavior and results, including absenteeism levels. Therefore, measuring employee performance is the performance or work results that have been achieved by employees within the scope of their responsibilities. There are five factors considered in measuring employee performance according to Dessler (2019), namely:

- (1) Quality of work, namely: acquisition, persistence, performance and acceptance;
- (2) Quantity of work, namely: volume of output and contribution;
- (3) Supervision, namely: input, suggestions, instructions, instructions or improvements;
- (4) Attendance, namely: compliance with rules, trust, and punctuality of work; and
- (5) Conservation, namely: maintenance, prevention of damage and repair.

Measuring employee performance is related to the employee's ability to properly complete assigned tasks according to planned targets. Therefore, job evaluation is very important in order to know the success that has been achieved by individuals and organizations so that the salary given is in accordance with employee achievements (Simamora, 2006).

Rivai et al. (2014:89) states that employee performance measurement guidelines consist of six indicators including:

- (1) Diligence,
- (2) Quantity and speed of completing work,
- (3) Thoroughness or accuracy,
- (4) Loyalty, relationships.
- (5) Work initiative, and
- (6) Cooperation and the ability to establish working

Performance measurement, especially for civil servants in Indonesia, initially referred to PP no. 30 of 2019 concerning employee performance assessment with the obligation to prepare Employee Work Targets (SKP). Thus, employee performance measurement in this research refers to SKP based on PP No. 30 of 2019 that systemically assess civil servant performance by collaborating SKP and work behavior. Employee performance assessment consists of 2 elements, namely SKP at 60% and work behavior at 40%. Employee performance assessment consists of two elements, namely SKP at 60% and work behavior at 40%.

SKP assessment includes indicators:

- (1) Quantity,
- (2) Quality, and
- (3) Time.

Meanwhile, work behavior consists of indicators:

- (1) Aspects of service orientation,
- (2) Commitment,
- (3) Work initiative,
- (4) Cooperation and
- (5) Leadership.

Next, it is synthesized with performance theory adopted from Mathis and Jackson (2011) and Dessler (2015).

This study refers to leadership theory stated by Greenleaf (1970) that the essence of a servant leader begins with a natural feeling to serve first, to ensure that "the highest priority needs of serving others take precedence", servant leadership is an approach that directs its goals for organizational development. Employees as equal partners, work together with subordinates for the success of the organization. (Greenleaf, 2008, Gilley et.al, 2011) leaders have a responsibility both towards the organization and morally as stakeholders of the organization (Williams's et.al, 2017). Leaders have a duty to help their followers achieve goals and provide direction as needed (House and Mitchell, 1974; Robbins and Judge, 2015). Path-goal theory. Leadership explains the impact of leader behavior on satisfaction and performance (Luthans, 2011: 124). Leadership is inspiring followers to commit to a shared vision that gives meaning to developing potential/performance. Previous research on leadership on performance by Hendik Arianto et al. (2020), Farida et al. (2020), Herso et al. (2020), Tripathi et al. (2021), Edi & Lenny (2021), Kadarusman & Bunyamin (2021), Donalan et al. (2022), Ludwikowska (2022), Yulyanti (2022), Abdul Syahid et al. (2022), Rizka & Sri Padmanty (2022), Dicka et al. (2022), Audia et al. (2022), Adjeng & Eka Triana (2022), Adnan & Shiva (2022).

Wang, et al. (2014) argue that social support is help or care by other people that an individual can feel, receive, and see. As an important environmental resource, social support influences a person's physical and mental health patterns and behavior. According to Maslihah (2011), there are 3 factors that can influence social support, namely: Empathy, namely sharing in other people's distress with the aim of anticipating emotions and motivation, social values and norms, which can be useful for teaching individuals to be able to carry out their obligations, social exchange, is a reciprocal relationship of social behavior between love, information and service. Indicators of Social Support according to Frese (1999) are as follows: Affective support and direct assistance.

Employee empowerment theory adopts a structural or psychological approach that high perceived employee empowerment is positively correlated with employee performance (Conger and Kanungo, 1988; Bowen and Lawler, 1995; and Chamberlin et al., 2018). Furthermore, Bowen and Lawler (1995:74) and Fernandez and

Moldogaziev (2013) state that to realize the benefits of (structural) empowerment, the following practices need to be shared with employees, namely:

- (1) Power to make decisions,
- (2) Information,
- (3) Knowledge, and
- (4) Appreciation.

In order to achieve the multiplier effect of additives on employee performance. Employee empowerment plays an important role in increasing innovative behavior, satisfaction with work and performance at both the team and organizational levels (Fernandez and Moldogaziev, 2013). Consistent with the opinion of Gibson et al (2015) that employee empowerment (individual empowerment) is providing opportunities and encouragement to employees to utilize their talents, skills, resources and experiences to improve performance by completing work on time.

Another view put forward by Newstorm (2015) is that providing empowerment boundaries is a process that provides greater autonomy to employees through sharing relevant information and providing control over factors that can influence work performance. Furthermore, various research streams confirm the assumption that employee performance is predicted to be significantly influenced by the empowerment delegated to employees (Choi et al., 2016; Andika and Darmanto (2020; Yulia and Baskoro (2021; Tripathi et al. 2021; Bartram et al. 2021; Rizki Zenia, 2021; Radiana Fitriati, 2021; Samsul and Agus 2021; Latif and Endang, 2022; Ekayanti, 2022; Setyanto and Koes, 2022; Prasetyo and Suparmi, 2022.

Based on the study conducted above, the research hypothesis is proposed as follows:

- H1: leadership has a positive and significant effect on the performance of ASN employees at Tanduale Bombana BLUD Hospital.
- H2: Leadership has a positive and significant effect on employee empowerment at Tanduale Bombana BLUD Hospital.
- H3: Leadership has a positive and significant effect on social support at the Tanduale Bombana BLUD Hospital
- H4: Employee empowerment has a positive and significant effect on employee empowerment at Tanduale Bombana BLUD Hospital.
- H5: Employee empowerment has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at the Tanduale Bombana BLUD Hospital.
- H6: Employee empowerment significantly mediates the influence of leadership on employee performance at the Tanduale Bombana BLUD Hospital.
- H7: Social support significantly mediates the influence of leadership on employee performance at the Tanduale Bombana BLUD Hospital.

RESEARCH METHODS

This research was conducted at BLUD Bombana Hospital, Southeast Sulawesi, Indonesia. By using a sample size, the subjects of this research were 88 Civil Servants at the Tanduale Bombana BLUD Hospital. Information is collected by providing a list of statements to obtain responses in the form of perceptions of the indicators for each

research variable. Hypothesis testing of direct and indirect effects (mediating role) using structural equation models.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Descriptive Analysis

Descriptive analysis emphasizes the average value of respondents' answers to the statements proposed by researchers. Descriptive data in this study includes original sample values, sample mean, standard deviation. These values are presented in Table 1, and include the average value of respondents' answers, maximum value, minimum value and standard deviation. These values are presented in Table 2.

Table 1: Original Sample Values, Sample Mean, Standard Deviation, t-statistic, and p-Value

	Original sample (O)	Sample average (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	t statistics (O/STDEV)	p values
Leadership -> Employee Empowerment	0.722	0.700	0.113	6.387	0.000
Leadership ->Social Suport	0.622	0.610	0.115	5.404	0.000
Leadership ->Performance	0.278	0.276	0.097	2.862	0.004
Employee Empowerment-->Performance	0.564	0.546	0.135	4.174	0.000
Social Suport -> Performance	0.059	0.071	0.096	0.615	0.538

Source: Primary data processed, 2024.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics of Research Variables

Leadership (X)	Mean	Min	Max	Standart Deviation
X1.1	4.08	1.000	5.000	0.681
X1.2	4.03	1.000	5.000	0.793
X1.3	4.05	1.000	5.000	0.726
X1.4	4.05	1.000	5.000	0.645
Government employees Empowerment (y ₁)				
Y1.1	4.17	1.000	5.000	0.647
Y1.2	4.06	1.000	5.000	0.726
Y1.3	4.17	1.000	5.000	0.678
Y1.4	4.18	1.000	5.000	0.590
Y1.5	4.04	1.000	5.000	0.622
Social Suport (Y ₂)				
Y2.1	4.13	1.000	5.000	0.593
Y2.2	4.03	1.000	5.000	0.670
Y2.3	3.21	1.000	5.000	0.832
Y2.4	4.08	1.000	5.000	0.711
Government employees Performance (Z)				
Z1.1	4.04	1.000	5.000	0.669
Z1.2	3.88	1.000	5.000	0.744
Z1.3	3.96	1.000	5.000	0.693
Z1.4	4.17	1.000	5.000	0.685
Z1.5	4.20	1.000	5.000	0.690
Z1.6	4.20	1.000	5.000	0.627

Source: Primary data processed, 2024.

This data shows that the average indicator value is greater than the standard deviation, so it can be concluded that the overall data shows a good representation.

Inferential Statistical Analysis

Inferential statistical analysis emphasizes factor loading values, R-square analysis, F-square analysis, hypothesis testing for direct and mediation effects.

Factor Loading

As presented in Figure 1, shows that all indicators have a loading factor value of more than 0.7, so that all indicators have the ability to reflect the variables, and can be used as a basis for hypothesis testing.

Figure 1: Structural Model

In the inner model, R-square, Q-square testing will be carried out on the dependent latent variable and bootstrapping to see significant values to determine the influence between variables.

R-square Analysis

The R-square value is the coefficient of determination on the endogenous construct. The R-square value criteria are 0.75 (strong), 0.50 (moderate), and 0.25 (weak). The R-square value in this research can be seen in Table 3 below:

Table 3: R-Square Value

	R-square	Adjusted R-square
Government Employees Empowerment (Y ₁)	0.521	0.520
Social Support (Y ₂)	0.387	0.386
Government Employees Performance (Z)	0.697	0.695

Source: Primary data processed, 2024.

In this research, there are 3 (three) variables which are influenced by other variables, namely the variable Government Employees Empowerment (Y₁) and social support (Y₂) as well as the performance of Government Employees Empowerment (Z) which is influenced by Leadership (X), the variable Government Employees Empowerment and social support as well. Is a mediating variable. Table 3 shows the R-square and adjusted R-Square values. The calculation results show that the Government

Employees Empowerment variable (Y_1) is 0.521 with an adjusted R-square value of 0.520 and for the social support variable (Y_2) it is 0.387 with an adjusted R-square value of 0.386 and the civil servant performance variable is 0.697 521 with a value adjusted R-square of 0.695. These results show that 52.0% of the Government Employees Empowerment variable (Y_1) is influenced by leadership (X) and 38.7% of the social support variable (Y_2) is influenced by leadership (X) and Government Employees Empowerment (Y_1).

F-square Analysis

To determine the impact of the leadership variable (X) on the Government Employees Empowerment (Y_1), social support (Y_2), and Government Employees Performance (Z) it can be seen from the F-Square value, the impact is strong if the f-square value is greater than 0.35; medium with a value of 0.15 - 0.35, and small if the value is smaller than 0.15. Overall F-square values are presented in Table 4 below.

Tabel 4: F-square

	Leadership	Government Employees Empowerment	Social Support	Government Employees Performance
Leadership		1.090	0.632	0.119
Government Employees Empowerment				0.330
Social Support				0.005

Source: Primary data processed, 2024.

Based on the data presented in Table 4, it shows that leadership has a strong influence on the variables of government employee's empowerment and social support, but moderately on government employee's performance. Government employee's empowerment has a strong influence on government employee's performance, while social support has a small influence on government employee's performance.

Testing the direct influence hypothesis

Table 5: Hypothesis Test Results

	Origin Sample (O)	t statistik (O/STDEV)	p values
Leadership -> Government Employees Empowerment	0.722	6.387	0.000
Leadership -> Social Support	0.622	5.404	0.000
Leadership -> Government Employees Performance	0.278	2.862	0.004
Government Employees Empowerment -> Government Employees Performance	0.564	4.174	0.000
Social Support -> Government Employees Performance	0.059	0.615	0.538

DISCUSSION

Based on the results of data processing as presented in Figure 1 and Table 5, it can be seen that in this research related to hypothesis testing, the results that can be concluded are as follows: the path coefficient of the influence of leadership on government employees empowerment is 0.722 and the significance value (p-sig) is 0.000, it is concluded that leadership has a significant positive effect on government employee's empowerment. The results of this test show that leadership which is reflected through its indicators, namely personal ability, leadership ability, organizing ability, will be able to increase government employees empowerment, which is reflected in the ability to manage

decisions in the workplace, transparency in sharing information, meaningfulness, competence and special impact. At the BLU Tanduale Hospital, Bombana.

The influence of leadership on social support shows a path coefficient value of 0.622 with a significance value (p-sig) of 0.000. This shows that leadership has a significant positive effect on social support. So if leaders increase their leadership role it will have an impact on increasing social support which is reflected in the indicators which include emotional support, appreciation support, instrumental support and informative support. This research is in line with research conducted by Wiranda Malau and Made Surya Putra (2022, Ping & Ely Siawati (2016).

The influence of leadership on government employee's performance shows a path coefficient of 0.278 with a p-sig value of 0.004. The test results show that leadership has a positive and significant effect on government employee's performance. These results show that if leadership is improved (through the indicators) then government employee's performance will be reflected in the indicators, namely: work quantity, work quality, work completion time, costs, service orientation, integrity and cooperation. The results of this research support research conducted by Handoko (2013) Siagian (2014) (Arianty, 2016). Nasution (2019) the effect of government employees empowerment on performance, the results of hypothesis testing show a path coefficient value of 0.564 with a p-sig value of 0.000.

The results of this test show that government employee's empowerment has a positive and significant effect on government employee's performance. So if an organization wants to improve government employee's performance as reflected in its indicators, the organization must first be able to increase government employee's empowerment as reflected in its indicators. The effect of social support on government employees performance, based on the results of the hypothesis test presented in Table 5, shows the path coefficient is 0.059 with a p-sig value of 0.538.

Based on the results of the hypothesis test, it can be concluded that social support has a positive effect on government employee's performance, but it is not significant. The results of this research are in line with research conducted by Muhaimin (2013); Darmasaputra (2013). The sixth hypothesis, namely the hypothesis that tests the role of government employee's empowerment variables in mediating the influence of leadership on government employee's performance, shows a t-statistical result of 3.472 with a p-sig level of 0.001. The test results show that social support is able to mediate the influence of leadership on civil servant performance, with a total effect of 0.407, when compared with the direct influence of leadership on civil servant performance of 0.278, the indirect influence is greater than the direct influence, so it can be concluded that the nature of the mediation is full mediation.

This indicates that the performance of civil servants at RSU BLUD Tanduale Bombana will increase even more if the existing leadership is able to increase government employee's empowerment so that it has a greater impact on improving the performance of civil servants. The seventh hypothesis in this research is to test the role of the social support variable as a mediating variable for the influence of leadership on the performance of civil servants at RSU BLUD Tanduale Bombana, showing a statistical t value of 0.613 with a p-sig of 0.540. These results indicate that social support is not significant as a mediating influence on leadership on the performance of civil servants at the Tanduale Bombana BLUD Hospital, but still has a positive impact. Conclusion the results of this research show that leadership has a

positive and significant influence on the performance of civil servants at RSU BLUD Tanduale Bombana. Likewise, government employee's empowerment also has a positive and significant effect on the performance of civil servants at RSU BLUD Tanduale Bombana, while social support has a positive but not significant effect. For the mediating role, it shows that government employee's empowerment is able to mediate the influence of leadership on civil servant performance, while social support is unable to mediate the influence of leadership on government employee's performance.

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